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ABSTRACT

This report presents the summary of the scientific and technical discussions in the ARIES WP7 Task 7.3 on the technological challenges for the design construction and operation of rings with Ultra-Low emittance and their relation with the beam dynamics parameters. The development of such rings is underpinned by the use of strong gradient magnets with significantly reduced aperture with respect to the conventional accelerator design of the previous generation. As a consequence, the vacuum vessel also must be designed with reduced apertures. It follows that all the other subsystem (e.g. diagnostics, injection, girders, and so on) must be adapted to this new set of requirements. Technological advances in these topics have opened the route to ever more aggressive lattice designs, hence reducing the equilibrium emittance to tens of pm. This report summarises the main topic discussed in the set of workshops supported by WP7.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

The construction and operation of ultra-low emittance rings is underpinned by the solution of a new set of technological challenges in the design of key subsystem like magnets and vacuum vessels, with significantly smaller apertures compared to the ones of third generation light sources in operation today. A wealth of novel concepts for the technology subsystems has been proposed and the corresponding technological challenges have been explored with strong R&D programmes. As a result, new more aggressive upgrade projects have opted for ambitious lattice design now reaching the few tens of pm. The Deliverable 7.3 consists in the report of the main activities and discussions on low emittance ring technology and its impact on the beam optics, held in the corresponding workshops.

1. Introduction

Storage rings generate ultra-low emittance electron beams (100 pm or less) by using strong focussing magnets. As an example, the medium energy (3 GeV) third generation light sources, operating with emittance in the order of few nm, required quadrupole gradients in the few tens of T/m, while the new generation with ultralow emittance require gradients approaching the 100 T/m. Simple rule of thumb for the design of such magnets show that the bore radius of quadrupole is reduced from ~20-30 mm radius to ~10-15 mm radius. Sextupoles and higher order multipoles follow similar scaling. Furthermore, the quest for compact design has driven the development of new concepts like longitudinal gradient dipoles and the wider use of solutions based on permanent magnets. The consequences of such size reduction on the vessel design have led to the extensive exploitation of NEG coating and strong R&D at several labs and industries is currently ongoing to solve a number of technology challenges related to the activation of such layers, the characterisation of their impedance and impact on the photon desorption yield. Several other subsystems are affected by the reduction of the pipe aperture, like Beam Position Monitors (BPM) design, and the overall integration of all elements in such compact lattices (e.g. girders, heat load management, stability, and so on) has been pushed to new limits with the ultra-low emittance rings.

These aspects have been the topics of Task 7.3 in ARIES WP7 (Rings for Ultra-Low Emittance - RUL ϵ). WP7 has supported networking activities and several workshops, two of which specifically dedicated to the discussion of technological aspect of low emittance rings subsystems,

- Topical workshop on diagnostics for ultra-low emittance rings, Chilton (UK), April 2018 [1]
- Advanced Low-Emittance Ring Technology (ALERT2019), with topical theme “rings with small apertures”, in Ioannina (Greece), July 2019 [2]

These workshops have been well attended (~40 delegates each). It should be mentioned that another critical technical subsystem in the design of ultra-low emittance ring is the injection process. New solutions and the corresponding R&D have been the object of a separate Task (Task

7.2 injection) in WP7 [3,4,5]. The present report is a summary of the most recent developments in the field and of the main points discussed in the ARIES WP7 Task. 7.3 workshops.

2. Magnets system for ultra-low emittance rings

During the ALERT 2019 workshop, six contributions were given on magnet design and technology for low emittance rings, dealing with subjects ranging from high gradient electromagnets [6,8], multipoles with permanent magnetic material [6,9] and dipoles with longitudinal gradient [6,7] and covering light sources upgrades such as the ESRF-EBS [6], the Canadian Light Source upgrade (CLS) [9], Diamond II [8,10] and the Swiss Light Source (SLS) upgrade [11], but also the CLIC damping rings [7].

2.1 HIGH GRADIENT ELECTROMAGNETIC QUADRUPOLES

For reaching high-gradient with electromagnetic quadrupoles, the current can be increased to the maximum permissible value, for a reduced bore radius. With the same technology (and same aperture), the gradient can be increased by using tapered poles and coils and raising the number of turns. An example for such a design is given in Fig. 2.1, where gradient for the upgrade of CLS is plotted versus Amp-turns (left) and good field region (right) for various apertures [9]. Different cobalt-iron magnetic alloys like vanadium permendur (Fe-Co) and type of poles can also be considered, as for the APS-U and ALS-U.

Fig. 2.1: Quadrupole gradient versus Amp-turns (left) and good field region (right) for various apertures (bore diameter), for the CLS 2 [9].

The resulting high-power consumption can be mitigated, within some limit, by the coil and pole design. At the same time, the field homogeneity is compromised by a current dependant dodecapole (b_6) multi-pole, which can be reduced with pole shaping. In that case, a trade-off with the maximum gradient is necessary. The second important challenge is reflected by the tight mechanical tolerances which comes naturally from the fact that small aperture magnets are more sensitive to mechanical errors. The magnetic error ΔB_n for multipole n at bore radius R is proportional to the mechanical error ε and inversely proportional to the bore radius. A mechanical tolerance of $\pm 40 \mu\text{m}$ is presently standard, whereas $\pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ is getting very expensive [6].

2.2 HIGH FIELD PERMANENT MAGNETS

An overview of quadrupole gradient over the bore radius is plotted in logarithmic scale in Fig. 2.2 (left). The resistive magnets (red points) achieve gradients up to 105 T/m at a radius of 13 mm. They are easily tunable and present a good homogeneity, as they are iron-dominated. On the other hand, permanent material (PM) magnets offer gradient of up to 560 T/m at smaller radius of 2.5 mm and come with several designs and technology offering tunability or only fixed gradient values. As the dependence of the gradient to the bore radius is trivial, a better representation is given in the right plot of Fig. 2.2, where the equivalent field (product of gradient with radius) is plotted versus the bore radius. For resistive magnets, the usual range of the field is between 1.1 to 1.3 T. The equivalent for Halbach type PM quadrupoles can reach 1.5 T with large outer-to-inner radii ratio. The field can exceed 2 T for “super-strong” PM and hybrid quadrupoles, like the CLIC QD0. The target for high field would be probably higher than 1.5 T, with apertures between 5 and 10 mm, with a $\pm 5\%$ tuning range.

Fig. 2.2: Overview of quadrupole gradient G in T/m (left) and equivalent field r (right) versus the bore radius r_0 [6].

Adjustable PM magnets including dipoles are also being considered and examples of such designs are shown in Fig. 2.3 for SPring-8 (left) and the CLIC drive beam turn-around loops (right).

Fig. 2.3: PM dipoles for SPring-8 (left) and the ZEPTO Dipole Design for the CLIC drive beam turn-around loops (right) [8].

2.3 DIPOLES WITH LONGITUDINAL GRADIENT AND SUPER-BENDS

Dipoles with longitudinal gradient are being considered in several low emittance rings for further lowering the horizontal emittance and for flexibility in the optics design, in particular dispersion manipulation [6,9,10,11]. An example of such a design is pictured in Fig. 2.4, for the CLIC damping rings. This particular magnet achieves a maximum field of 2.3 T, while following a hyperbolic field profile decay, using different PM material and adjustable gap for the low, mid and high field region. At the same time a quadrupole gradient is introduced. This allows a reduction of the emittance by a factor of 7, as compared to the one of the standard Theoretical Minimum Emittance (TME) cell.

Fig. 2.4: Longitudinally variable dipole with gradient for the CLIC damping rings (left) and corresponding field profile variation along the magnet's length (right) [7].

Another trend in low emittance rings is the use of superbends, as hard x-ray sources. Such a superbend is being studied for the upgrade of SLS. An overview of the available superconductors is shown in Fig. 2.5 [11]. Depending on the wire technology, higher fields could be achieved for moderate critical current densities at 4.2 K. In the specific case of the SLS upgrade, the conceptual design, including magnetic, thermal, mechanical and quench protection system, of a 4 T peak field conduction-cooled superbend based on NbTi wire technology has been finalised. A 6 T peak field magnet with Nb₃Sn cable and an even higher field dipole based on High-Temperature Superconductors is also being considered.

Fig. 2.5: Summary of critical current density dependence on the applied magnetic field for various available superconductors [11].

3. Vacuum systems ultra-low emittance rings

Small aperture vessels are characterised by a low vacuum conductivity, hence pumping with NEG coating has become the standard for supplementing the additional pumping in ultra-low emittance accelerators. Virtually all new projects employ NEG coating to some extent. The proposed solutions differ in the amount of chamber that is coated, ranging from coating both arcs and straight vessels to coating limited to simple vessel in the straight sections. NEG has also the additional benefit of reducing the photon desorption yield of the coated chamber.

The main difficulties associated to coatings can be summarised in

- uniformity requirement on the coating
- impedance effect of the coating
- logistic in the activation procedure (in-situ vs ex-situ activation)

The coating thickness is a compromise between vacuum performance and the conductivity of the layer. Extensive studies performed at Daresbury Laboratories show that NEG thickness of up to 1 μm, provides good vacuum characteristics while not impacting the surface resistance of the material at the typical frequencies of interest (~10 GHz), which remains essentially that of the substrate [12]. Fig. 3.1 shows that changes in the impedance occur at frequency ranges that are generally too high for the typical bunch length for operation in ultra-low emittance rings. However, achieving the required uniformity of the coating in complex geometries still remains a technology issue: 250 nm uniformity on a 2 μm thick coating was reported on the SLS NEG coating trials [13].

Fig. 3.1: Resistivity as a function of the NEG thickness for different frequencies. The yellow band indicates the typical values chosen in accelerators.

The impact of the coating on the resistive surface depends on the conductivity of the material and on the deposition process. The materials used (Titanium-Zirconium-Vanadium) generate a conductivity larger than Stainless Steel. Different material choices are still part of an intense R&D and it was recently reported that pure Zirconium has better sticking probabilities than Ti-Zr-V and comparable to more complex compounds such as Hf-Zr-V, Ti-Hf-V, Ti-Zr-Hf [12].

The coating process (sputtering with wires) influences the morphology of the coating. The NEG structure can be broadly subdivided in two, dense and columnar NEG, with dense NEG offering a lower surface resistivity. Several studies have investigated the frequency dependence of the conductivity up to very high frequency, as shown in Fig. 3.2 [14]. Discrepancies in the measured values of the conductivity as a function of the frequency have been attributed to surface roughness effects that are thought to affect both the DC and the AC conductivity.

Fig. 3.2: Frequency dependence of the NEG conductivity.

In situ activation is based prevalently on the use of heater tapes wound around the chamber to reach a temperature of 150-180 °C. This choice requires space in the magnet bore aperture to allow the permanent installation of such heater tapes. Sirius experience shows that the thickness of these tapes can be reduced to 400 μm [15]. The activation temperature should be guaranteed to all the coated part and this is a potential problem in case of complex geometries (e.g. with keyslots or tapers). Experimental campaigns on the possibility of activating the NEG with synchrotron radiation are ongoing but no conclusive results are yet available.

In summary, it appears that several technical solutions concerning the extent to which NEG is used are equally feasible. The present trend sees a tendency to design fully coated chamber (MAX IV, SIRIUS, SOLEIL, PETRA IV) while other projects have opted for a mixture of NEG coating straight chamber with classical antechambers in the arcs (ESRF-EBS, Diamond II) while NEG coating for reduced photon desorption is the main reason for the full NEG coating proposed for SLS II [13].

Special care should be paid to the Ti coating of ceramic chambers used in pulsed magnets in off axis injection schemes (e.g. septum and four kickers bump). In fact, any dis-uniformity in the coating generates different effect on the magnetic field pulse, including transient oscillations in the stored beam during Top-Up. The process of coating is eased by manufacturing procedures of the ceramic chamber involving the manufacturing of two separate halves, assembled by soldering along the midplane of the beam. This ensures precision machining of the inner part of the ceramic and a better quality of the coating [16].

4. Collective effects in ultra -low emittance rings

Impedance and collective effects and their relation with the new technologies described above were discussed in the topical workshop ALERT 2019 [2]. There were altogether five contributions two of which were from the light source community (SOLEIL and PSI) and three others addressed impedance issues in rings built for the high energy physics experiments (two from CERN and one from INFN, Napoli). A point of common concern was the characterisation impedance which arises from a thin coating (typically of sub-micron level thickness) on the inner surface of the vacuum chamber wall. Such thin coating can be generally classified in two categories: One is the metallic coating of poor conducting materials (such as NEG) made on a good conductor wall (such as copper). The other is the coating of good conducting materials (such as titanium) on dielectric walls to mitigate the impedance issues. There is a clear trend today that modern synchrotron rings make intensive use of both types of thin coatings for good technical grounds. The overall characteristics of the impedance of coated chambers, in particular their frequency dependence, must, as a consequence, be well understood theoretically, numerically and experimentally.

4.1 ONGOING STUDIES FOR FUTURE ULTRA-LOW-EMITTANCE RINGS

A review on impedance and beam instabilities created by low gap vacuum chambers was given [17]. Though it is a global trend of accelerators today to go for lower gaps, it is particularly true for all ultra-low emittance rings under design and built in the light source community, known as DLSRs (Diffraction Limited Storage Rings). These rings utilise the MBA (Multi-Bend Achromat) principle of dividing dipoles into many pieces and strongly focus the beam at each of them towards the TME (Theoretical Minimal Emittance) condition. The strong focusing in turn requires low gap chambers in the magnet sections to have smaller distance between magnetic poles. A table and a figure were shown summarizing the global trend for half gap b 's (or inner radius of a cylindrical pipe in the arcs) considered for some of the typical rings under design or construction (Fig. 4.1 (left)), where the values tend to be below 10 mm. As a marked case, SOLEIL is currently considering employing b of down to 5 mm for the magnet sections for its upgrade. Another noticeable trend is that several different b values are considered within the magnet sections such as for ESRF-EBS, reflecting the effort to maximise the aperture where it is possible for better beam dynamics and lifetime performance.

Fig. 4.1: (left) Principal vertical half aperture b adopted in several existing and future light sources versus their machine energies; (right) Transverse impedance budget obtained for SIRIUS (taken from F.-E. De Sá, LER2016)

Such small b values for the beam duct create vacuum pumping issues. Here, one of the most promising solutions considered is NEG coating on the inner surfaces, as it has already been seen to work successfully in several rings such as MAXIV as the last good example [18]. In view of relatively poor electric conductivity of the constituents of NEG (titanium, zirconium and vanadium), the impact of NEG coating on the machine impedance must be well understood. Studies indicate that thin NEG coating (micron level) on the inner surface of ordinary metallic chambers, in the normal frequency range seen by the beam, does not modify much the real part of the impedance, which is normally responsible for beam instabilities, while the imaginary part is increased by roughly a factor of two, suggesting that physical phenomena such as bunch lengthening and coherent detuning would be enhanced [19].

Considering the b -dependence of the machine impedances, whether they are of geometric or resistive-wall origins, which scale typically as b^{-1} longitudinally and b^{-3} transversely, it must be said that more effort is required to optimise the geometrical and material aspects of vacuum components to keep the same level of machine impedance as earlier rings of the same size. However, it must be pointed out that for MBA lattices there is a general trend that the average beta functions are lower than those of the earlier rings. One may therefore anticipate that in the transverse plane the increased impedance is effectively compensated. Novel BPM and the so-called impedance-free flanges developed for SIRIUS can be listed as good examples of the effort in this direction [20]. The impedance budget built for SIRIUS (Fig. 4.1 (right)) shows the typical situation where the resistive-wall impedance is dominating the budget and that due to NEG coating, the imaginary part is found nearly double as compared to the real part in the main frequency range of interest as pointed out earlier.

Preliminary studies of the resistive-wall instability were made for the SOLEIL upgrade using a Vlasov solver in the frequency domain, where lowering of the instability threshold for smaller b 's ($\phi = 2 \times b$ in the figure) is clearly found (Fig. 4.2 (left)).

Fig. 4.2: (left) Vertical resistive-wall instability threshold computed using a frequency domain (Vlasov type) method for SOLEIL upgrade; (right) Beam loss observed at SOLEIL originating in beam induced vacuum chamber heating [19].

The impact of the linear optics, optics nonlinearity, as well as harmonic cavity lengthening that are expected to influence (mitigate) significantly the coherent motions must be studied systematically. Simulation tools need to be extended accordingly to be able to incorporate these effects. Regarding the impedance, not only must we care for beam instability, but generally the beam-induced heating of vacuum components gives more stringent tolerance, as an incidence on a single component may block the machine operation. The persistent beam loss existing at SOLEIL when it is operated at 500 mA in $\frac{3}{4}$ fill is understood to be caused by beam-induced machine heating that in turn produces local outgassing leading to FBII (Fast Beam-Ion Instability) [21]. Since transverse bunch-by-bunch feedback is constantly running to fight against resistive-wall instability, the sudden appearance of FBII which keeps getting stronger leads finally to a beam loss (Fig. 4.2 (right)).

A study of longitudinal single bunch instability was presented by A. Citterio (PSI) [22]. The main concern is understanding if the momentum compaction α , which is tuned to negative or to a very small value in magnitude due to the ultra-low emittance lattice design, enhances the instability to an unacceptable level. Here again we encounter a situation where a continued effort to improve the lattice performance ends up creating a significant impact on the collective effects. Related to this study, a dedicated experiment with beam was carried out in April 2019 at KARA among KARA, SOLEIL and PSI under the support of ARIES (WP7-WP11), to measure the microwave instability threshold as a function of the value of α , where the measured data suggested that the threshold is lowered when α is negative [23]. Numerical studies carried out by SLS for SLS-II focused upon the dependence of instability on α , the NEG and bunch lengthening with harmonic cavities (active and passive) (Fig. 4.3 (right)). Of particular interest and importance for the community is that the group managed to use two tracking codes, *elegant* and *mbtrack* and crosschecked the results, such as on the threshold and intensity-dependent bunch profiles, where the overall agreement was found to be quite satisfactory (Figs. 4.3). Such efforts are highly appreciated by the entire community. From these studies it was confirmed that NEG does not worsen the threshold and that the threshold is lower when α is negative. The last outcome, along

with the experimental results at KARA gave the SLS team some elements to reconsider their negative α lattice for SLS-II.

Fig. 4.3: (left) Beam energy spread versus single bunch current calculation using elegant and mbtrack including passive or active harmonic cavities, to identify the microwave instability threshold indicated with an arrow; (right) Comparison between elegant and mbtrack of the longitudinal bunch profile as a function of bunch current

4.2 SEMI-ANALYTICAL IMPEDANCE CHARACTERISATIONS

Semi-analytical methods to obtain the coupling impedance of beam ducts that have some specific conditions on their inner surface, typically layers of coating, are investigated. C. Zannini of CERN in [2] presented an overview of the subject showing how the impedance can be classified, with terms such as those due to geometric variations and to material-dependent or electric conductivity related origins. Evaluation methods of the impedance (analytical, numerical 3D, bench measurement) were also reviewed. Then, more detailed properties of the non-geometric impedance were presented. The relative importance of the impedance of coated chambers in modern accelerators was highlighted. It was shown how the longitudinal and transverse impedance can be decomposed into products of a geometric form factor depending on the chamber cross sections (known as the Yokoya factor), another geometric factor related to the chamber radius b , and to the part depending on the materials of the chamber determining the frequency-dependent EM characteristics of the impedance (Fig. 4.4 (left)). Examples were shown such as how the impedance of a ceramic chamber can be reduced with a thin titanium coating (Fig. 4.4 (right)).

Fig. 4.4: (left) Illustration of how the longitudinal and transverse impedances are composed of geometric form factors, chamber radius and material properties-dependent surface impedance; (right) Illustration of how metallic coating reduces the ceramic chamber impedance

The second contribution was given by S. Arsenyev, who presented the details of the surface impedance which was introduced in the former. Again the main focus of the latter was on the non-geometric impedance. In contrast to the field matching technique which is widely known and applied to obtain the impedance of coated materials such as those available today with the code IW2D developed at CERN, it was shown that there is another effective method by solving for the surface impedance. How coupling impedance is related to the surface impedance under the Leontovich boundary condition under the assumption $|\epsilon_1 \mu_1| > \epsilon_0 \mu_0$, and how the surface impedance can be obtained were presented (Fig. 4.5 (left)). Some specific examples of this approach were shown solving the surface impedance in problems such as the two-layer model, linear conductivity model and surface roughness model (Fig. 4.5 (right)) [24].

Fig. 4.5: (left) Illustration of how longitudinal and transverse impedance of a beam pipe can be related to the surface impedance; (right) measured surface roughness and its modelling to obtain the surface roughness impedance via surface impedance

4.3 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION OF COATING MATERIALS

Development of a bench measurement to perform electromagnetic characterisation of coating materials in the sub THz range and its application to NEG coating was presented by A. Passarelli (INFN, University of Naples, CERN). The objective was to develop a reliable, handy and

inexpensive system for the electromagnetic characterisation of coating materials in the sub THz range. A time domain THz spectrometer TERA K15 was employed. A special circular wave guide was designed and fabricated at CERN (Fig. 4.6 (left)). The EM characterisation is made by measuring the signal attenuation inside a DUT with coating deposited. The process was first evaluated analytically and compared with numerical simulations using CST, where good agreement was obtained. Two NEG coated slabs (3.96 and 3.68 μm coating thickness) were then measured. The results were consistent between the two slabs and the fitted electric conductivity of roughly $8 \times 10^5 \text{ S/m}$ was also in agreement with expectations (Fig. 4.6 (right)) [25].

Fig. 4.6: (left): Illustration of DUT (Device under Test) arrangement; (right): Experimentally obtained electric conductivity of a NEG coated slab fitted from the bench measurement data

4.4 SUMMARY

With decreasing gaps of many of the future ring vacuum chambers, the beam coupling impedance is expected to get furthermore enhanced. Along with lattice designs pushing towards technical limits on their side, the evaluation of collective effects is confronted to take also into consideration nonlinear single particle dynamics to draw correct conclusions. Impedance arising from thin metallic coating of poor electric conducting materials on a good conductor wall or coating of good conducting materials on dielectric walls must be well understood and controlled both theoretically, numerically and experimentally. Works presented in the session go well along this direction showing the state-of-the-art progress. Simulation studies using different codes have shown good ways to benchmark codes and better confirm obtained results. Effect of NEG coating on beam instabilities requires further thorough studies.

5. Diagnostics for ultra-low emittance rings

Ultra-low emittance rings require stringent constraints on the stability of the electron beam. Specific needs of most recent light sources push these requirements to fraction of the beam size and divergence ($\sim \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim \mu\text{rad}$) over a frequency range up to 1 kHz. This stability should be achieved under different operating conditions (e.g. charge per bunch).

The design of the Beam Position Monitor (BPMs) system in operating light source partially meets already these requirements, as several light sources operate with pm emittance in the vertical plane. Improvements are ongoing in the BPM electronics to equalize the behaviour of the channels and their stability with the concept of “pilot tone”. This activity is now developing as a collaborative effort involving several laboratories (ELETTRA, Diamond, DESY, ALS, NLS-II).

The “pilot tone” technique traces back to concepts in telecommunication developed in the 1950s and consists in sending to the receiver a well-defined signal, on top of the signal to be measured, so that the pilot signal can be used as reference and correct for possible distortions. It provides for real-time correction of channel to channel variations on BPM inputs caused by factors unrelated to real beam motion, such as temperature differences between similar components on adjacent inputs. This has been attempted many times with limited success, such as the NSLS-II system where it failed due to the different temperature characteristics of analogue SAW filters. This manifests as a difference in channel attenuation between the carrier and pilot tone frequencies, which itself varies with temperature. The solution for NSLS-II was to rely on active electronics rack temperature stabilization. At the ALS, the pilot tone concept was successfully incorporated into NSLS-II BPM design after an extensive effort to replace the analogue front-end bandpass filters and development of FPGA code. The recent experience at Elettra involved an in-tunnel analogue front-end responsible for the generation and injection of the pilot tone onto the four signal cables. Fig. 5.1 illustrates the beam spectra and the pilot tone at one BPM button. The pilot tone was 1.5 revolution harmonics away from the carrier. Deliberately cooling one of the four bandpass filters induced tens of microns of apparent position readback shift without correction, while application of pilot tone correction reduced this to below the level of one micron. A comparable level of correction was similarly achieved while abusing other components in one of the four processing chains [26].

Fig. 5.1: typical spectrum of a BPM button signal with pilot tone at ELETTRA

Another challenge specific to ultra low emittance ring is the design of four buttons in such reduced aperture vessels. The impact on the machine impedance has to be traded with the required

sensitivity of the button monitors. Example of BPM geometries in small aperture circular vessels are given in Fig. 5.2 from the HEPS project in Beijing [27].

Fig. 5.2: (left) button BPM geometry on small aperture circular vessel; (right) button and feedthrough detail.

From the discussions at the various workshops, it clearly transpired that stability is a key problem in the operation of the new generation of rings and requiring a close integration of different design aspects. The stability of the photon beam at the sample is the ultimate goal and anything that affects this is important and should be minimised. This connects and integrates any solution that aims at optimized solutions, including floor structure, girders, magnets, orbit stability, water noise or temperature sensitivity. The engineering design cannot be regarded in isolation and many areas should be looked at collectively, even procurement, to find the best solution in terms of stability, cost and efforts available. Specific task forces on stability are created at different laboratories [28]

6. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

ARIES WP7 Task. 7.3 has dealt with the major technological issues in the development of ultra low emittance rings, consisting in the design of innovative magnets design, vessel and vacuum concept with reduced aperture where the concept of NEG coating is extensively used. Many other technical subsystems have to adapt to such reduced apertures. A large number of novel technical solutions have emerged and have been reviewed in two topical workshops organised by ARIES WP7.

The activity of the WP7 Task 4.3 will continue by promoting further networking activities to answer the questions left open and to provide support to the new design projects and the ongoing commissioning of the new rings ESRF-EBS [29] and Sirius [30].

7. References

- [1] Topical Workshop on Diagnostics for Ultra-Low Emittance Rings, Diamond Light Source, UK, 14th-15th April 2018. Slides in <https://indico.cern.ch/event/682952/overview>
- [2] Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/overview>
- [3] R. Bartolini, M. Boege, Final report on injection schemes and injection studies, ARIES Project, deliverable D7.2 in <https://edms.cern.ch/document/1817751/1.0>
- [4] TWISS: First Topical Workshop on Injection and Injection Systems, BESSY-II, Berlin (Germany), (2017), slides in <https://indico.cern.ch/event/635514/>
- [5] TWISS: Second Topical Workshop on Injection and Injection Systems, PSI, Villigen (Switzerland), (2019), slides in <https://indico.psi.ch/event/6972/>
- [6] G. Le Bec, "High gradient magnets, PM multipoles and dipoles with longitudinal gradients", Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494707/attachments/1877610/3093721/ALERT2019_LeBec.pdf
- [7] M. A. Domínguez et al., "Development of a high-field longitudinal gradient dipole at CIEMAT", Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494708/attachments/1878599/3094382/ALERT19_CLIC_DR_Longitudinal_Gradient_Dipole_SN.pptx
- [8] B. Shepherd, "Development of Adjustable Permanent Magnet Quadrupoles", Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494717/attachments/1876993/3094157/2019-07-11_BJAS_-_Development_of_Adjustable_Permanent_Magnet_Quadrupoles_ALERT19.pptx
- [9] L. Dallin, "Electromagnets with High Gradients for CLS 2.0", Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494718/attachments/1877538/3092295/CLS2_magnets.pptx
- [10] A. Shahveh, "Magnet Design for Diamond-II Upgrade", Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494720/attachments/1877819/3092960/AS_2019_07_10_ALERT19.pptx
- [11] C. Calzolaio, "Magnets for the SLS upgrade", Advanced Low Emittance Rings' Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494721/attachments/1878173/3094001/SLS2_calzolaio.pdf

-
- [12] O. Malyshev, “NEG coatings as complex solutions for particle accelerators”, Advanced Low Emittance Rings’ Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494645/attachments/1877364/3095958/V2_ALERT_2019_-_O_Malyshev_12-06-2019.pdf
- [13] A. Zandonella, “Vacuum concept for SLS 2.0”, Advanced Low Emittance Rings’ Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494662/attachments/1877766/3092780/Vacuum_Concept_for_SLS_2.0_ALERT_2019_12.07.2019.pdf
- [14] E. Koukovini-Platia et al. “Electromagnetic characterisation of NEG properties between 220-300 GHz and 500-750 GHz for the CLIC damping ring”, PRAB, **20**, 011002, (2017).
- [15] P. H. Nallin al., “The Sirius heating system for the in-situ NEG activation”, IPAC19, (2019), <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/ipac2019/papers/thpts004.pdf>
- [16] D. Einfeld, “The ceramic chambers of the ESRF-EBS”, Advanced Low Emittance Rings’ Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494644/attachments/1877421/3093169/ESRF-Ceramic-Chambers.pdf>
- [17] R. Nagaoka, “Impedance and instabilities of low gap chambers”, in Advanced Low Emittance Rings’ Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019, https://indico.cern.ch/event/819665/contributions/3494675/attachments/1877459/3092131/Impedance_Instabilities_R.Nagaoka_ALERT2019.pdf
- [18] P.F. Tavares et al., “Status of the MAXIV Accelerators”, IPAC2019, Melbourne, Australia
- [19] R. Nagaoka, K.L.F. Bane, J. Synchrotron Rad. (2014). 21, 937–960
- [20] R.M. Seraphim et al., “Vacuum System Design for the SIRIUS Storage Ring”, IPAC2015, Richmond, Virginia, USA
- [21] R. Nagaoka et al., “Fast Beam-Ion Instability Arising from Local Outgassing”, LER workshop TWIICE, EuCARD-2, Synchrotron SOLEIL, 2014
- [22] A. Citterio, “overview of collective effects in SLS 2.0”, in Advanced Low Emittance Rings’ Technology Workshop (ALERT 2019), Ioannina, Greece, 2019.
- [23] P. Schreiber et al., “Status of Operation with Negative Momentum Compaction at KARA”, IPAC2019, Melbourne, Australia
- [24] S. Arsenyev, D. Schulte, “Modelling Wake Impedance of a Rough Surface in Application to the FCC-hh Beamscreen”, IPAC2018, Vancouver, Canada
- [25] A. Passarelli et al., Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 21, 103101 (2018)

- [26] G. Brajnik et al., “Advantages of the pilot tone approach in sub- μm BPM application for low emittance machines”, in Topical Workshop on Diagnostics for Ultra Low Emittance Rings, Diamond Light Source, April 2018,
https://indico.cern.ch/event/682952/contributions/2937104/attachments/1635439/2609025/Brajnik-DeMonte_-_TW-DULER.pdf
- [27] S. Yanfeng et al., “Overview of HEPS diagnostics design and the efforts on beam instrumentation R&D”, in Topical Workshop on Diagnostics for Ultra Low Emittance Rings, Diamond Light Source, April 2018,
https://indico.cern.ch/event/682952/contributions/2959778/attachments/1637740/2613747/Overview_HEPS_beam_diagnostics_design_and_the_efforts_on_beam_instrumentation_RD.pdf
- [28] B. N. Jensen, “MAX IV stability task force update”, in Topical Workshop on Diagnostics for Ultra Low Emittance Rings, Diamond Light Source, April 2018,
https://indico.cern.ch/event/682952/contributions/2956168/attachments/1636272/2610735/MAX_IV_Stability_Task_Force_TW-DULER_April_2018.pdf
- [29] P. Raimondi, “The ESRF-EBS: the extremely brilliant source project”, Journal of Synchrotron Radiation, pg. 8-15, **29-6**, (2016).
- [30] A.R.D. Rodrigues et al., “Sirius light source status project”, IPAC18, (2018),
<http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/ipac2018/papers/thxgbd4.pdf>